

Ultrasonic studies on the molecular interactions of gadolinium soaps in benzene-dimethylformamide mixture

Seema Agrawal^{a*} and S. K. Upadhyaya

P.G. Department of Chemistry, S. S. L. Jain College, Vidisha-464 001, Madhya Pradesh, India

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Christian Eminent College, Indore, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : agrawal.seema24@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 05 October 2012, revised 07 November 2012, accepted 26 December 2012

Abstract : The ultrasonic measurements of the solutions of gadolinium caprylate and laurate in a mixture of 50/50 benzene-dimethylformamide (v/v) have been used to evaluate critical micellar concentration, ultrasonic velocity and various acoustical parameters at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K. The trends in acoustical parameters indicates that there are significant molecular interaction between soap and solvent molecules. The values of cmc increase with the rise in temperature and molecules of gadolinium soaps do not aggregate appreciably in dilute soap solution below the cmc.

Keywords : Ultrasound, compressibility, gadolinium soaps, cmc.

Introduction

The importance of metal soaps has already been realised owing to their proven utility in different industries as dispersants¹, lubricants²⁻⁴, catalysts^{5,6}, stabilizers⁷ and corrosion inhibiting agents^{8,9}. In spite of many applications in industry the fundamental characteristics of rare-earth metal soaps and their role in various industrial preparations, have not yet been investigated systematically. The physico-chemical characteristic and structure of soaps can be controlled up to a certain extent by the methods and conditions of their preparation. The studies of metallic soaps are therefore of great significance for their applications in various industries under different conditions. A number of workers have used the ultrasonic technique for the determination of the ion-solvent interaction¹⁰⁻¹³ and the results are found to be in agreement with the results of other workers.

The present work deals with the measurements of the ultrasonic velocity of the solutions of gadolinium soaps in 50% benzene and 50% dimethylformamide mixture (v/v) in order to determine, specific acoustic impedance, intermolecular free length, internal pressure, apparent molar compressibility, molar sound velocity, relative association, relaxation strength and solvation number.

Materials and methods :

The chemical used were of AR grade. Gadolinium caprylate and laurate were prepared by the direct metathesis of corresponding potassium soaps with a slight excess of gadolinium acetate solution at 50–60 °C under vigorous stirring. The precipitated soap was washed several times with double distilled water and finally with acetone. The soap was dried under reduced pressure. The purity of the soap was checked by elemental analysis. The results agreed with the theoretically calculated values.

The ultrasonic velocity of the solutions of gadolinium soap was measured on a multi frequency ultrasonic interferometer M-X3 Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi at a frequency of 1 MHz at 40 ± 0.05 °C. The uncertainty of the velocity measurement was $\pm 0.2\%$. The densities and viscosities were measured with Pyknometer and Ostwald type viscometer, respectively. The volume of the Pyknometer was 10 ml and the accuracy of density result was ± 0.0001 .

Results and discussion

The micellization process in organic solvent and mixed organic solvent is somewhat different from that in aqueous solutions. The main cause of micellization¹⁴ in or-

ganic solvent in the energy change due to dipole-dipole interactions between the polar head groups of the soap molecules. The association begins at very low concentration in organic solvents and results in the formation of very much smaller aggregates than in H₂O.

Using the measured values of ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity of the solutions, adiabatic compressibility, inter molecular free length, internal pressure, Rao's number, specific acoustic impedance, molar sound velocity, relative association and solvation number were calculated at different temperatures (Tabel 1).

Ultrasonic velocity increases linearly with increase of concentration of gadolinium caprylate and laurate at different temperatures below the cmc. Whereas the plots of ultrasonic velocity vs soap concentration are characterized by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite

soap concentration which corresponds to the cmc value of the gadolinium soap (Tabel 2).

The increase in velocity, density and viscosity with increase in concentration suggests increase in cohesive forces due to intermolecular interactions. The ultrasonic velocity decreases with increase in temperature in 50% benzene + 50% dimethylformamide mixture (v/v). The variation of ultrasonic velocity with soap concentration follows the relationship¹⁵ :

$$v = v_0 + GC \tag{1}$$

where v_0 is the ultrasonic velocity in the solvent and G is Garnsey's constant. The value of Garnsey's constant in the mixture of 50% benzene and 50% dimethylformamide (v/v) for gadolinium caprylate and laurate are mentioned in Table 2. The values of Garnsey's constant increase with increase in chain length of the soap molecule. How-

Table 1. The values of density (ρ), viscosity (η), ultrasonic velocity (v) and other acoustical parameters of gadolinium caprylate in 50% benzene + 50% dimethylformamide mixtures (v/v)

Concentration ($C \times 10^3$) (g mol ⁻¹)	Soap solution density (ρ) (g ml ⁻¹)	Ultrasonic velocity ($v \times 10^{-5}$) (cm/s)	Adiabatic compressibility ($\beta \times 10^{11}$) (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	Apparent molar compressibility ($-\phi_k \times 10^7$) (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	Solvation number (S_n)
1.0	0.9144	1.2743	6.735	2.16	212.3
2.0	0.9158	1.2753	6.714	2.20	107.7
3.0	0.9174	1.2761	6.694	2.23	72.8
4.0	0.9190	1.2769	6.674	2.24	55.3
5.0	0.9206	1.2775	6.656	2.26	44.8
6.0	0.9220	1.2778	6.643	2.05	37.6
7.0	0.9230	1.2782	6.631	1.92	32.5
8.0	0.9238	1.2785	6.622	1.75	28.6
9.0	0.9244	1.2788	6.615	1.63	25.6
10.0	0.9250	1.2793	6.606	1.45	23.1

Molar sound velocity (R)	Relative association (R_a)	Relaxation strength (r)	Specific acoustic impedance ($Z \times 10^{-5}$)	Inter molecular free length (L_f) (Å)	Viscosity (η)	Internal pressure (π_i)
5045.93	3.7029	0.3657	1.1652	0.5284	0.7640	4.1885
5069.77	3.7049	0.3647	1.1679	0.5276	0.7660	4.1893
5092.18	3.7069	0.3639	1.1706	0.5268	0.7675	4.1901
5114.50	3.7088	0.3631	1.1734	0.5260	0.7695	4.1910
5136.41	3.7106	0.3625	1.1760	0.5253	0.7715	4.1920
5159.05	3.7125	0.3622	1.1781	0.5248	0.7730	4.1928
5184.05	3.7146	0.3618	1.1797	0.5243	0.7738	4.1933
5209.48	3.7167	0.3615	1.1810	0.5240	0.7745	4.1937
5236.48	3.7196	0.3612	1.1821	0.5237	0.7755	4.1941
5263.73	3.7212	0.3607	1.1833	0.5233	0.7762	4.1944

Fig. 1. Ultrasonic velocity vs concentration plots of gadolinium caprylate in 50% benzene and 50% dimethylformamide mixture (v/v) at various temperatures.

Table 2. The values of cmc, Garnsey's constant, limiting molar compressibility and constant S_k of gadolinium caprylate and laurate at different temperatures

Temp. (K)	Gadolinium caprylate				Gadolinium laurate			
	cmc $\times 10^3$ (g mol $^{-1}$)	Garnsey's constant (G)	φ_k^0	S_k	cmc $\times 10^3$ (g mol $^{-1}$)	Garnsey's constant (G)	φ_k^0	S_k
303	5.2	9.0×10^6	1.48	4.13	5.0	9.1×10^6	1.53	4.50
308	6.2	8.1×10^6	1.43	4.15	6.0	8.3×10^6	1.50	4.86
313	6.9	6.8×10^6	1.39	4.20	6.3	7.3×10^6	1.47	5.14
318	7.2	6.2×10^6	1.36	4.26	7.0	7.1×10^6	1.44	5.33

ever, these values decrease with increasing temperature.

The values of adiabatic compressibility (β) of the solutions of gadolinium caprylate and laurate (Table 1), decrease with increasing soap concentration. The decrease in adiabatic compressibility is attributed to the fact that the soap molecules in dilute solution are ionized into metal cations and fatty acid anions to some extent. These ions are surrounded by a layer of solvent molecules firmly bound and oriented towards the ions. The orientation of solvent molecules around the ions is attributed to the influence of the electrostatic field of the ions. So that the internal pressure increases, this lowers the compressibility of the solutions.

The adiabatic compressibility, β is found to obey Bachem's relationship¹⁶ :

$$\beta = \beta_0 + AC + BC^{3/2} \quad (2)$$

where β_0 is the compressibility of solvent, C is the molar concentration and A and B are constants. The values of constants A and B have been obtained from the intercept and slope of linear plots of $\beta - \beta_0/C$ vs \sqrt{C} are mentioned in Table 2.

The apparent molar properties of gadolinium soaps are found to be dependent on the concentration of the solutions. The apparent molar compressibility φ_k , can be expressed by the relationship :

$$\Phi_k = \frac{1000}{C\rho_0} (\rho_0\beta - \beta_0\rho) + \frac{M\beta_0}{\rho_0} \quad (3)$$

where M is molecular weight of soap.

Fig. 2. Apparent molar compressibility vs square root of concentration plots of gadolinium caprylate in 50% benzene and 50% dimethylformamide mixture (v/v) at various temperatures.

The values of the apparent molar compressibility ϕ_k varies linearly (Table 1) with squareroot of concentration below the cmc at all temperatures of gadolinium soaps obeying Gucker's limiting law¹⁷.

$$\phi_k = \phi_k^0 + S_k C^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where S_k is a constant. The value of ϕ_k^0 and S_k for the solution were evaluated from the intercept and slope of the linear plots of (Fig. 2) ϕ_k vs $C^{1/2}$ below the cmc (Table 2). The positive value of S_k signifies a considerable soap-solvent interaction below the cmc.

The intermolecular free length L_f is the predominant factor for determining the ultrasonic velocity in solution and is related to the compressibility by the relationship $K(\beta)^{1/2}$, where K is the temperature dependent Jacobson's constant¹⁸.

The values of intermolecular free length (Table 1) decrease with increasing concentration and chain length of the soap. The decrease in the values of intermolecular free length with increasing concentration indicate that there is a significant soap-solvent interaction¹⁹ due to which the structural arrangement considerably affected. Analysis of data indicates that L_f values increase with the increase in temperature. This may be due to the thermal

agitation²⁰ and loosening of intermolecular attraction with the rise in temperature and the association of molecules with increase in concentration.

The specific acoustic impedance, Z is the product of ultrasonic velocity and density of the medium. The values of specific acoustic impedance with increasing soap concentration are recorded in the Table 1.

The increase in the value of Z with increasing C can be explained on the basis of lyophobic interaction between soap and solvent molecules which increases the intermolecular distance leaving relatively wider gap between the molecules and thus becoming the main cause of impediment to the propagation of ultrasound waves and ultimately affects the structural arrangements.

The adiabatic compressibility data have been used to calculate the solvation number of soaps. The assumption has been made that the ions as well as the solvent molecules in immediate contact are compressible. This is because the ions add some electrostatic stiffening on the adjacent solvent molecules which is considered to be equivalent to a large internal pressure on these solvent molecules. Pasynskii²¹ defined the solvation number as the number of solvent molecules present in the primary

solvation sheath and is given by the relationship.

$$S_n = \frac{n_0}{n} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{V}\beta}{n_0 \bar{V}_0 \beta_0} \right) \quad (5)$$

where V is the volume of solution containing n_0 moles of soap and V_0 is the molar volume of the solvent. The results show that the solvation number increases with increasing concentration and chain length of the soap. In post micellization region, the values of solvation number, S_n exhibit a marked change which may be attributed to greater intake of solvent molecules above the cmc to reduce the repulsive forces acting between polar heads of ionic micelles.

The internal pressure π_i of gadolinium soap solution in 50% benzene and 50% dimethylformamide have been calculated by the equation²² :

$$\pi_i = bRT [K\eta/v]^{1/2} [P^{2/3}/\bar{M}^{7/6}] \quad (6)$$

where b = stands for the cubic packing factor which is assumed to be 2 for all liquids and solutions, K = temperature independent constant (4.28×10^9), R is gas constant ($8.31433 \text{ JK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$), T is temperature on absolute scale and M is effective molecular weight of the solution.

The increase in temperature makes the free length to increase due to the thermal expansion of liquid (Table 1). These results show that the value of internal pressure increases with the increase in soap concentration. However the increase in temperature results in the decrease of internal pressure²³.

The values of molar sound velocity²⁴ increase with the increase in soap concentration and chain length of the soap molecule. An increase in temperature increases the molar volume, probably due to decrease in density of these soap solutions. The molar sound velocity is however independent of temperature.

The values of relative association²⁵ R_A and solvation number for gadolinium soap in 50% benzene and 50% dimethylformamide mixture (v/v) decrease with increase in soap concentration. However these values increase with increasing temperature. The decrease in relative association, R_A has been attributed either to the decreased association between soap and mixed organic solvent molecules at higher concentration or increasing solvation of ions.

The increase in the values of relative association with rise in temperature is attributed to the decrease in solvation with rise in temperature.

The results of ultrasonic measurement of gadolinium caprylate and laurate in 50% benzene + 50% dimethylformamide (v/v) indicate that there is a significant interaction between soap and solvent molecules and the values of various acoustical parameters calculated with the help of ultrasonic, density and viscosity data are in fair agreement with the results of other workers¹⁴.

Conclusion :

The ultrasonic velocity throws light on evaluation of acoustical parameters of gadolinium caprylate and laurate in a mixture of 50/50 benzene-dimethylformamide (v/v) at different temperatures. The results confirm that there is a significant interaction between the soap and solvent molecules in dilute solution^{26,27}. Data on ultrasonic velocity shows that gadolinium soaps behave as weak electrolyte in nonaqueous medium and soap molecules do not aggregate appreciably below the cmc.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. A. K. Gangele, Principal, S. S. L. Jain P.G. College, Vidisha for providing laboratory facilities.

References

1. R. P. Varma and Bahadur, *Cellul. Chem. Technol.*, 1974, **8**, 189.
2. T. G. Sokolova, L. Yu. Ishchuk, N. S. Goshko, V. A. Vrokopchuk and V. V. Sinitsyn, *Kolloidn. Zh.*, 1971, **33**, 895.
3. M. B. Nakonechaya, I. V. Lend'el, N. V. Samoilenko and A. S. Kravchenko, *Sb. Tr. Vses. Ob'edin. Neftekhim*, 1973, **5**, 52.
4. A. Bouman, *Ind. Chim. Belge.*, 1950, **37**, 29.
5. E. S. Lower, *Ind. Parfum.*, 1947, **2**, 319.
6. M. P. Baspyatov and V. I. Polstyanoi, *Maslob. Zhir. Prom.*, 1962, **28**, 14.
7. A. J. Lehman, *Assoc. Food Drug Off. U. S., Q. Bull.*, 1951, **15**, 82.
8. J. E. O. Mayne and D. V. Rooyen, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1954, **4**, 384.
9. W. C. Johnson, U.S. Pat. 1958, **2**, 858,285 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1959, **53**, 3733).
10. D. S. Allam and W. H. Lee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **6049**, 432.

11. S. Prakash and C. V. Chaturvedi, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **10**, 669.
12. S. Prakash, N. Prasad and O. Prakash, *J. Chem. Engg. Data*, 1977, **22**, 51.
13. S. Prakash, S. Singh, N. Prasad and R. Singh, *Rev. Acust.*, 1978, **9**, 34.
14. K. N. Malhotra and M. Anis, *Monatshefte fur Chemie.*, 1995, **126**, 637.
15. R. Garnsay, R. J. Boe, R. Mahoney and T. A. Litovitz, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1969, **50**, 5222.
16. C. Bachem, *Z. Physik.*, 1936, **101**, 541.
17. F. T. Gucker, *Chem. Rev.*, 1933, **13**, 111.
18. B. Jacobson, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, **6**, 1485.
19. H. Eyring and J. F. Kincaid, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, **6**, 620.
20. D. P. Singh and K. P. Prabhakar, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrason.*, 1994, **61**, 41.
21. A. Pasynsky, *Acta Physico-Chem. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1939, **8**, 385; *J. Phys. Chem. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1938, **11**, 608.
22. K. Raju and C. Rakkappan, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2011, **23**, 19.
23. T. Sumathi and A. N. Kannappan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 807.
24. M. R. Rao, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1940, **14**, 109; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1941, **9**, 682.
25. A. Waissler, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1947, **15**, 210.
26. K. Kishore and S. K. Upadhyaya, *Tenside Surf. Det.*, 2010, **47**, 184.
27. K. Kishore and S. K. Upadhyaya, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrason.*, 2011, **33**, 29.